

Protocol for a systematic review of land- and water-management technologies for resilient agriculture in the Sahel: Insights from climate analogues in sub-Saharan Africa

Wilson Nguru^{1*}, Issa Ouedraogo², Cyrus Muriithi¹, Stanley Karanja¹, Michael Kinyua¹ and Alex Ndua¹.

¹ International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), Duduville Campus Off Kasarani Road P.O. Box 823-00621, Nairobi, Kenya; ciatkenyainfo@cgiar.org

² International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), Almadies, Parcelles 22, Zone 10 Lot 227, Dakar, Sénégal

* Correspondence: wilson.maina@cgiar.org

Abstract

In sub-Saharan Africa, land degradation and climate change threaten food security by reducing soil productivity and water availability. Soil and water conservation (SWC) technologies can restore soil health, enhance moisture retention, and support crop growth under adverse conditions. This review identifies SWC technologies applied in climatically similar African regions with the aim of informing adoption in Senegal, particularly in Sédhiou and Tambacounda regions. Using K-means clustering on 19 WorldClim bioclimatic variables, 35 comparable countries were identified, of which 17 met inclusion criteria based on data availability and $\geq 60\%$ climatic similarity. Around 85 technologies were reviewed, including water harvesting, soil-moisture conservation, and erosion control, assessed for their compatibility across rainfall patterns, and land gradients and uses. The review highlights 12 successful technologies across Africa with high potential for cross-border transfer and upscaling in Senegal's agroecological context. While countries such as Burkina Faso, Kenya, and Malawi lead in technology adoption and diversity, Senegal lags behind due to institutional gaps, limited funding, and weak extension systems. The findings highlight the importance of site-specific water management for improving soil conservation, biodiversity protection, climate adaptation, and food security, and emphasize the need for policy integration, stakeholder empowerment, private-sector engagement, and cross-border learning to accelerate adoption.

1. Background

Soil and water are the foundational resources for agricultural production and environmental sustainability (Shang & Xie, 2024), yet their degradation poses a critical threat to food security across sub-Saharan Africa. Global transformations, including climate change, population expansion, and unsustainable agricultural practices, have accelerated the loss of arable land (Gomiero, 2016) and compromised water availability (Mishra, 2025). This crisis is particularly acute for small-scale farmers, who are disproportionately affected by the

interconnected challenges of land degradation, soil moisture scarcity, and increasingly erratic rainfall patterns.

The African continent exemplifies the urgency of this challenge. The African Union Commission estimates that 65% of Africa's arable land is affected by degradation (Vlek et al., 2010), contributing to declining soil fertility and agricultural productivity. Furthermore, the United Nations Environment Programme reports that desertification affects around 46% of Africa's land area (Reich et al., 2019), with over half of this area at high or very high risk of further degradation. These environmental crises form a negative feedback loop: land degradation reduces the soil's water retention capacity, which in turn exacerbates water scarcity and reduces the land's resilience to climate impacts, leading to a downward spiral of declining agricultural productivity.

In response to these challenges, a diverse array of soil and water conservation (SWC) technologies has been developed and implemented across the continent. These technologies, which include water harvesting, soil moisture conservation, and erosion control measures, can restore soil health, enhance moisture retention, and support crop growth under adverse conditions (Abdelhak, 2024). However, the adoption of these practices remains highly uneven across regions with similar agroecological conditions.

Senegal, situated in West Africa, experiences a predominantly arid to semi-arid climate that poses significant challenges to its predominantly rainfed agricultural system. The country lags behind neighbouring nations such as Burkina Faso and Niger in the adoption of proven land and water management technologies, despite facing similar climatic pressures (Ewulo et al., 2025). This lag is attributed to institutional gaps, limited funding, and weak extension systems, among other factors (World Bank, 2009).

This systematic review addresses a critical knowledge gap by employing a novel climate analogue approach to identify proven SWC technologies from regions with similar climatic conditions to Senegal's Sédhiou and Tambacounda regions. By systematically identifying, classifying, and evaluating technologies that have succeeded in climatically analogous areas, this review aims to provide a robust, evidence-based framework for technology transfer and upscaling. The findings are expected to inform policy, guide investment, and support the development of resilient agricultural systems in the Sahelian region of Senegal and beyond.

2. Objectives

Primary Objective: To identify and synthesize soil and water conservation technologies from climatically analogous regions in sub-Saharan Africa for potential adoption in Senegal's Sédhiou and Tambacounda regions.

Secondary Objectives:

- To classify technologies by function (water harvesting, soil moisture management, efficient irrigation).
- To analyze adoption patterns and success factors across different countries.

- To develop slope-specific recommendations for Senegalese context.

3. Methods

3.1 Study Design

This research will be conducted as a systematic review following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) as outlined by Moher et al. (Moher et al., 2009) guidelines. The primary objective is to systematically identify, catalogue, and synthesize the range of land- and water-management technologies practiced across climatically analogous regions in sub-Saharan Africa. The synthesis will be exclusively qualitative and descriptive in nature. The core methodology involves creating a comprehensive evidence map to categorize and list all identified technologies, detailing their implementation contexts and key characteristics. The review will not involve quantitative pooling or statistical analysis of outcomes like crop yields. The final and crucial phase of the synthesis will be a feasibility assessment, where the identified technologies are evaluated against the specific biophysical context of the target Senegalese regions (Sédhiou and Tambacounda). The primary filter for this assessment will be slope compatibility, given the predominantly flat to gently undulating terrain (0-10% slopes) of these areas. This process will result in a finalized set of practical, context-appropriate technology recommendations for Senegal.

3.2 Eligibility criteria

Studies will be included if they are from the 17 pre-identified climate-analogue countries, focus on soil and water conservation technologies, were published between 2005-2023, and are peer-reviewed articles, technical reports, or working papers in English or French. Studies will be excluded if they are from non-target countries, focus solely on crop breeding or chemical interventions, are book chapters or theses, or lack a clear methodology or reported outcomes.

3.3 Information sources

- Databases:
 - Scopus
 - Web of Science
 - Google Scholar and Google search (for grey literature)

- Search Terms:

Search strings combined terms such as “*water management*,” “*soil and water management*,” “*sustainable land management*,” “*rainwater harvesting*” with additional keywords like “*technologies*,” “*practices*,” “*arid regions*,” “*semi-arid Africa*,” and country-specific identifiers (e.g., “*Ethiopia*,” “*Kenya*,” “*Sahel*”).

3.4 Study Selection Process

The study selection will follow a three-phase process. First, records will be identified through database searches and duplicates will be removed. Second, the unique records will undergo title/abstract screening against the eligibility criteria, followed by a full-text assessment of potentially relevant studies. Finally, a definitive inclusion decision will be made based on the full-text review, with reasons for exclusion documented at this stage. The entire process will be reported using a PRISMA flow diagram.

3.5 Data Extraction

A standardized form will be used to extract the following data from included studies:

- a) Study identification (authors, year, country);
- b) Technology characteristics (name, category, description);
- c) Implementation context (slope, rainfall, soil type, crops);
- d) Reported outcomes and adoption factors (drivers, barriers); and
- e) A qualitative assessment of transferability to the Senegalese context.

3.6 Quality Assessment

Study quality will be assessed based on methodological transparency, contextual relevance, and clarity of outcome reporting. This assessment will not be used to exclude studies, but to inform the interpretation of findings and identify limitations in the evidence base during synthesis.

3.7 Data Synthesis

The synthesis will proceed in three tiers:

- a) **Descriptive Mapping** to catalogue technologies by country and type.
- b) **Feasibility Filtering** to identify technologies suitable for the Senegalese context based primarily on slope compatibility (0-10%); and
- c) **Recommendation Development** to produce a finalized list of prioritized technologies with key implementation considerations.

4 Outputs and dissemination

Key outputs will include a peer-reviewed manuscript, a PRISMA flow diagram, comprehensive tables of technologies organized by country, a slope-specific recommendation table for Senegal, and a policy brief for stakeholders. All data extraction files and the analysis dataset will be made publicly available to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

5 Ethical considerations

This review raises no major ethical concerns as it uses exclusively previously published data. All sources will be properly cited and acknowledged. We commit to transparent reporting of methods and limitations.

6 Funding and conflicts of interest

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